

Seismic Evaluation Of Tall Buildings With Shear Walls And Soft Stories

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the seismic response of a G+15 reinforced concrete framed commercial building under different shear wall and soft-storey configurations using ETABS. Eight structural models were examined, including a fully infilled baseline frame, shear wall configurations at corners and along principal directions, a corner-plus-core wall system, soft-storey arrangements at lower and intermediate levels, and a combined soft-storey model retrofitted with shear walls and a core wall. Equivalent Static Method, Response Spectrum Analysis and Time History Analysis were used to compare fundamental time period, design seismic base shear, inter-storey drift and storey displacement under Seismic Zone IV conditions. The results show that structural configuration strongly influences stiffness and lateral response. The corner-plus-core wall configuration showed the shortest fundamental period, while soft-storey arrangements increased deformation demand. Model 6 recorded the highest storey displacement, and soft-storey cases concentrated drift at irregular levels. The study confirms that strategic shear wall placement and core wall integration improve lateral stiffness, control drift and reduce the vulnerability associated with vertical stiffness irregularities in tall RC framed buildings.

Keywords: ETABS, G+15 building, shear wall, soft storey, response spectrum analysis, time history analysis, base shear, storey drift

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Rapid urbanization has increased the need for taller reinforced concrete structures. Such buildings must resist gravity loads and dynamic lateral forces generated by earthquakes and wind. In reinforced concrete framed buildings, masonry infill walls contribute significantly to lateral stiffness during the elastic stage. However, when infill walls are removed at one or more levels, a soft-storey condition is created, producing a sudden change in lateral stiffness and increasing the vulnerability of the structure under seismic excitation.

Soft-storey configurations are commonly introduced at lower levels to provide parking or functional open spaces. The resulting stiffness discontinuity can concentrate deformation demand in the affected storeys. Shear walls and core walls are therefore considered important lateral load-resisting components because they improve stiffness, reduce lateral displacement and help control drift. This study presents a comparative seismic investigation focused on the performance of a G+15 RC structure with shear wall and soft-storey configurations.

1.2 Objectives

- To investigate a G+15 storey building and evaluate the structural behaviour of multi-storey reinforced concrete framed structures.
- To analyze the structural response of the building by implementing shear walls in different configurations and locations.
- To assess the effect of lateral and dynamic loading through shear wall and core wall integration.
- To evaluate soft-storey behaviour by removing infill masonry walls at selected storey levels.
- To compare the structural responses obtained from Equivalent Static Method, Response Spectrum Analysis and Time History Analysis.
- To compare fundamental time period, base shear, inter-storey drift and lateral displacement.

1.3 Scope of Work

The scope of the study is limited to the dynamic behaviour of a G+15 RC framed commercial building subjected to seismic actions. The same geometric and material parameters are used across eight analytical models. The

results are interpreted through ETABS output parameters including fundamental natural time period, design seismic base shear, inter-storey drift and storey displacement.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Earlier studies on high-rise and multi-storey RC buildings consistently show that vertical irregularities such as soft storeys amplify lateral displacement and drift demand. Zhang et al. [1], Patel et al. [3], Singh and Verma [4], Ahmed et al. [5], Das and Roy [10], and Reddy et al. [12] reported that soft-storey or vertical irregularity effects increase vulnerability and may lead to damage concentration at weak levels.

Several works also emphasize the role of shear walls as an efficient lateral load-resisting system. Kumar and Sharma [2], Rao and Kulkarni [6], Choudhary et al. [7], Mehta et al. [9], Karthik and Prasad [11], and Mishra et al. [14] found that shear wall location and configuration substantially affect displacement, drift, torsional behaviour and base shear. Centrally placed core walls and well-distributed wall layouts are generally more effective in improving stiffness and overall seismic performance.

The reviewed literature supports the need for a focused comparison of multiple shear wall and soft-storey configurations using dynamic analysis methods. The present study addresses this need by evaluating eight G+15 RC building models under Equivalent Static Method, Response Spectrum Analysis and Time History Analysis.

III. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Methods of Seismic Analysis

Three methods of seismic analysis were adopted. The Equivalent Static Method represents earthquake action by distributing equivalent lateral forces along the height of the structure. The Response Spectrum Analysis method estimates modal contributions and combines peak modal responses to obtain design values. Time History Analysis evaluates the structural response step-by-step under time-varying seismic excitation and is useful for capturing the transient dynamic behaviour of the system.

The study compared the above methods using ETABS results for the same G+15 building geometry and material properties. The principal response parameters considered were fundamental natural time period, base shear in both principal directions, inter-storey drift and storey displacement.

3.2 Building Details

Table 1. Details of the analyzed G+15 RC structure.

Parameter	Value
Type of structure	Commercial building (G+15)
Plan dimension	22x24.5m
Grade of concrete	M40 (for columns)
Grade of concrete	M30 (for beams, slab)
Column size	300x1500, 300x1200
Beam size	300x600
Slab thickness	150mm
Seismic zone	zone IV
"Importance factor"	1.2.
"Response reduction factor"	5 (S M R F)
Soil type	TypeII
Imposed load	3.0KN/m2
floor finish	1.5KN/m2
Density of masonry	19KN/m3
Wall load on beams	15.675KN/m3
Density of RCC	25KN/m3
Grade of steel	fe415,fe500
wall thickness	300mm
Floor tallness	3.35m
Height of building	52.75m

3.3 Analytical Model Configurations

Table 2. Analytical models considered in ETABS.

Model	Configuration	Description
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Model 1	Baseline model	G+15 RC framed building with full masonry infill brick walls.
Model 2	Corner shear wall model	Full masonry infill walls with shear walls positioned at the outer corners.
Model 3	X-direction shear wall model	Full masonry infill walls with shear walls aligned along the X-direction.
Model 4	Y-direction shear wall model	Full masonry infill walls with shear walls aligned along the Y-direction.
Model 5	Corner plus core wall model	Full masonry infill walls with shear walls at peripheral corners and a central core wall.
Model 6	Ground soft-storey model	Masonry infill walls from the 4th floor upward, leaving storeys 1, 2 and 3 open.
Model 7	Intermediate soft-storey model	Masonry infill walls removed at storeys 3, 4 and 5.
Model 8	Combined retrofit model	Soft-storey arrangement retrofitted using shear walls and a central core wall.

Figure 1. ETABS model view for Model 1: regular G+15 storey building.

Figure 2. ETABS model view for Model 2: shear wall at corners.

Figure 3. ETABS model view for Model 3: shear wall along X direction.

Figure 4. Additional ETABS view for Model 3.

Figure 5. ETABS model view for Model 4: shear wall along Y direction.

Figure 6. ETABS model view for Model 5: corner shear wall and central core wall.

Figure 7. ETABS model view for Model 6: soft storey at storeys 1, 2 and 3.

Figure 8. Additional ETABS view for Model 6.

Figure 9. ETABS model view for Model 7: soft storey at storeys 3, 4 and 5.

Figure 10. ETABS model view for Model 8: soft-storey model with shear wall retrofit.

Figure 11. Additional ETABS view for Model 8.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

4.1 Fundamental Natural Time Period

The fundamental time period was evaluated from the undamped free-vibration characteristics of the structure. The variation in time period reflects differences in stiffness among the structural configurations. Models with increased lateral stiffness show shorter periods, while soft-storey configurations tend to elongate the vibration period.

Table 3. Fundamental natural time period of the analyzed models.

Model No.	Equivalent Static Method	Time History Analysis	Response Spectrum Analysis
1	2.67	2.78	2.892
2	1.724	1.724	1.724
3	2.429	2.429	2.429
4	1.322	1.322	1.322
5	1.252	1.245	1.245

6	2.643	2.743	2.743
7	2.42	2.42	2.334
8	1.269	1.269	1.269

TIME PERIOD COMPARISON USING DIFFERENT ANALYSIS METHODS

Chart 1. Fundamental natural time period for the analyzed models.

The table and chart show that Model 5 has the lowest reported period, while Model 1 and Model 6 exhibit comparatively higher periods. The results reflect the influence of stiffness enhancement through shear walls and stiffness reduction due to soft-storey behaviour.

4.2 Design Seismic Base Shear

Base shear is the total lateral seismic force acting at the base of the structure. The reported values differ across models because each configuration changes the stiffness profile, mass participation and lateral load transfer mechanism.

Table 4. Design seismic base shear values for ESM, THA and RSA.

Model No.	ESM UX	ESM UY	THA UX	THA UY	RSA UX	RSA UY
1	4032.75	6354.08	4032.62	6533.976	4029.6749	6533.5875
2	6529.88	9449.25	6529.66	9449.49	6529.4741	9015.16
3	7234.77	6515.106	6080.95	6190.37	7235.789	6515.1029
4	4271.6	10036	4271.53	10035.84	4272.6009	10036.00016
5	8376.1	11773	27169.7854	13584.89	8376.0994	11773.0001
6	3501.02	5995.67	1943.48	5495.58	3501.0692	5537.6647
7	3444.63	5440.94	3443.28	5440.938	31206.8339	44921.28
8	6656.841	7113.714	3328.25	3556.769	6656.849	7113.724

The base shear results indicate that wall placement and core wall integration significantly influence lateral force demand. Model 5 produces high base shear values, consistent with increased stiffness from corner shear walls and a central core wall. Soft-storey models generally show changes in base shear and displacement response due to localized stiffness discontinuity.

4.3 Inter-Storey Drift

Inter-storey drift is the relative lateral displacement between consecutive floor levels and is a critical indicator of deformation demand. The drift profiles obtained from ETABS vary across the eight models because of differences in shear wall location, core wall contribution and soft-storey stiffness reduction. Detailed numerical

drift tables are retained in Appendix A, while the original reported charts are included below as core visual evidence.

STOREY DRIFT VARIATION ALONG BUILDING HEIGHT – MODEL 1

Chart 2. Storey drift profile for Model 1: regular G+15 storey.

STOREY DRIFT VARIATION ALONG BUILDING HEIGHT – MODEL 2

Chart 3. Storey drift profile for Model 2: shear walls at corners.

**STOREY DRIFT VARIATION ALONG BUILDING HEIGHT – MODEL 3
(REGULAR MODEL WITH SHEAR WALL IN X DIRECTION)**

Chart 4. Storey drift profile for Model 3: shear wall in X direction.

**STOREY DRIFT VARIATION ALONG BUILDING HEIGHT – MODEL 4
(REGULAR MODEL WITH SHEAR WALL IN Y DIRECTION)**

Chart 5. Storey drift profile for Model 4: shear wall in Y direction.

STOREY DRIFT VARIATION ALONG BUILDING HEIGHT – MODEL 5 (REGULAR MODEL WITH SHEAR WALL IN CORNER & CORE WALL AT CENTER)

Chart 6. Storey drift profile for Model 5: corner shear walls with core wall.

STOREY DRIFT VARIATION ALONG BUILDING HEIGHT – MODEL 6 (MODEL WITH SOFT STOREY AT 1, 2 & 3 STOREY)

Chart 7. Storey drift profile for Model 6: soft storey at storeys 1, 2 and 3.

STOREY DRIFT VARIATION ALONG BUILDING HEIGHT – MODEL 7 (MODEL WITH SOFT STOREY AT 3, 4 & 5 STOREY)

Chart 8. Storey drift profile for Model 7: soft storey at storeys 3, 4 and 5.

STOREY DRIFT VARIATION ALONG BUILDING HEIGHT – MODEL 8 (REGULAR MODEL WITH SOFT STOREY ALONG WITH SHEAR WALL IN CORNER & CORE WALL AT CENTER)

Chart 9. Storey drift profile for Model 8: soft-storey model with shear wall retrofit.

The drift charts show that the soft-storey configurations concentrate deformation demand at the irregular levels, while shear wall and core wall configurations control drift by increasing lateral stiffness. Among the drift tables, the highest reported drift occurs in the soft-storey cases, especially in Model 7.

4.4 Storey Displacement

Storey displacement is the absolute lateral translation of a floor level relative to the base. The reported displacement values demonstrate that soft-storey arrangements increase lateral displacement demand, while shear wall and core wall layouts reduce displacement by improving the lateral load-resisting mechanism. Detailed displacement tables are retained in Appendix B.

STOREY DISPLACEMENT – MODEL 1 (REGULAR MODEL G+15 STOREY)

Fig. 6.4.1: Storey Displacement Comparison for Model 1 (Regular Model G+15 Storey) Using Equivalent Static Method (ESM), Time History Method (THM), and Response Spectrum Method (RSM) in X and Y Directions.
 Source: ETABS Analysis Results (2026) – Compiled by Researcher.

Chart 10. Storey displacement profile for Model 1: regular G+15 storey.

STOREY DISPLACEMENT – MODEL 2 (REGULAR MODEL WITH SHEAR WALL AT CORNERS)

Fig. 6.4.2: Storey Displacement Comparison for Model 2 (Regular Model with Shear Wall at Corners) Using Equivalent Static Method (ESM), Time History Method (THM), and Response History Method (RHM) in X and Y Directions.
 Source: ETABS Analysis Results (2026) – Compiled by Researcher.

Chart 11. Storey displacement profile for Model 2: shear walls at corners.

STOREY DISPLACEMENT – MODEL 3 (REGULAR MODEL WITH SHEAR WALL IN X DIRECTION)

Fig. 6.4.3: Storey Displacement Comparison for Model 3 (Regular Model with Shear Wall in X Direction) Using Equivalent Static Method (ESM), Time History Method (THM), and Response History Method (RHM) in X and Y Directions.

Source: ETABS Analysis Results (2026) – Compiled by Researcher.

Chart 12. Storey displacement profile for Model 3: shear wall in X direction.

STOREY DISPLACEMENT – MODEL 4 (REGULAR MODEL WITH SHEAR WALL IN Y DIRECTION)

Fig. 6.4.4: Storey Displacement Comparison for Model 4 (Regular Model with Shear Wall in Y Direction) Using Equivalent Static Method (ESM), Time History Method (THM), and Response History Method (RHM) in X and Y Directions.

Source: ETABS Analysis Results (2026) – Compiled by Researcher.

Chart 13. Storey displacement profile for Model 4: shear wall in Y direction.

**STOREY DISPLACEMENT – MODEL 5
(REGULAR MODEL WITH SHEAR WALL IN CORNER & CORE WALL AT CENTER)**

Fig. 6.4.5: Storey Displacement Comparison for Model 5 (Regular Model with Shear Wall in Corner & Core Wall at Center) Using Equivalent Static Method (ESM), Time History Method (THM), and Response History Method (RSM) in X and Y Directions.

Source: ETABS Analysis Results (2026) – Compiled by Researcher.

Chart 14. Storey displacement profile for Model 5: corner shear walls with core wall.

**STOREY DISPLACEMENT – MODEL 6
(MODEL WITH SOFT STOREY AT 1, 2, 3 STOREY)**

Fig. 6.4.6: Storey Displacement Comparison for Model 6 (Model with Soft Storey at 1, 2, 3 Storey) Using Equivalent Static Method (ESM), Time History Method (THM), and Response History Method (RSM) in X and Y Directions.

Source: ETABS Analysis Results (2026) – Compiled by Researcher.

Chart 15. Storey displacement profile for Model 6: soft storey at storeys 1, 2 and 3.

Chart 16. Storey displacement profile for Model 7: soft storey at storeys 3, 4 and 5.

STOREY DISPLACEMENT – MODEL 8
(REGULAR MODEL WITH SOFT STOREY ALONG WITH SHEAR WALL IN CORNER & CORE WALL AT CENTER)

Fig. 6.4.8: Storey Displacement Comparison for Model 8 (Regular Model with Soft Storey Along with Shear Wall in Corner & Core Wall at Center) Using Equivalent Static Method (ESM), Time History Method (THM), and Response History Method (RSM) in X and Y Directions.

Source: ETABS Analysis Results (2026) – Compiled by Researcher.

Chart 17. Storey displacement profile for Model 8: soft-storey model with shear wall retrofit.

The results show that Model 6 records the highest storey displacement, particularly under Time History Analysis in the Y direction. This confirms the vulnerability of structures with lower-level soft storeys and highlights the need for lateral stiffness enhancement in such configurations.

V. DISCUSSION

The comparative analysis confirms that seismic response is highly sensitive to the placement of lateral load-resisting elements. The baseline model and soft-storey models exhibit longer periods and larger deformation demand because of lower effective stiffness. Conversely, shear wall and core wall configurations shorten the time period and improve the ability of the structure to resist lateral deformation.

The base shear results must be interpreted with stiffness effects in mind. A stiffer configuration can attract larger base shear while still controlling displacement and drift more effectively. The combination of peripheral corner

walls and a central core wall therefore provides improved stiffness and load transfer capacity, even though the reported base shear demand is high.

The soft-storey cases demonstrate a clear concentration of drift and displacement response. Model 6, with open lower storeys, is particularly vulnerable because reduced stiffness at lower levels increases lateral translation. Model 7 also shows high drift demand at the intermediate irregularity. Model 8 demonstrates the beneficial effect of retrofitting through shear walls and a central core wall.

The Time History Analysis ground-motion record details were not separately specified in the reported data. Therefore, the interpretation is restricted to the reported ETABS output values without introducing additional earthquake record assumptions.

VI. CONCLUSION

- The study evaluated eight G+15 RC framed building configurations using Equivalent Static Method, Response Spectrum Analysis and Time History Analysis.
- Soft-storey configurations increase structural vulnerability by reducing lateral stiffness and concentrating deformation demand at the irregular storey levels.
- Model 6 exhibits the highest storey displacement among the reported configurations, confirming the critical behaviour of lower-level soft-storey arrangements.
- Inter-storey drift values remain lower at the base and top levels and increase at intermediate levels depending on the stiffness distribution of each model.
- The corner-plus-core wall configuration improves lateral stiffness and reduces the fundamental time period compared with more flexible configurations.
- The strategic use of shear walls and core walls is effective in reducing lateral displacement and controlling drift in tall RC buildings with soft-storey conditions.
- The results support the use of properly located shear walls as a practical strengthening and seismic-resisting measure for G+15 RC framed buildings in Seismic Zone IV.

REFERENCES

- 1) Zhang, Y., Liu, H., and Wang, J. (2025). Seismic Performance Assessment of High-Rise Buildings with Soft Storey and Shear Wall Systems. *International Journal of Structural Engineering*, 18(2), pp. 125-139.
- 2) Kumar, R., and Sharma, P. (2024). Comparative Analysis of Shear Wall Locations in Multi-Storey Buildings Subjected to Earthquake Loads. *Journal of Earthquake Engineering and Structural Dynamics*, 16(4), pp. 210-225.
- 3) Patel, N., Desai, K., and Shah, M. (2024). Dynamic Behavior of Soft Storey Buildings under Response Spectrum Analysis. *International Journal of Civil and Structural Engineering Research*, 12(1), pp. 45-59.
- 4) Singh, A., and Verma, S. (2023). Evaluation of RC Tall Buildings with Soft Storey Using Time History Analysis. *International Journal of Advanced Structural Engineering*, 15(3), pp. 180-193.
- 5) Ahmed, F., Khan, M., and Ali, S. (2023). Seismic Behavior of High-Rise Buildings with Vertical Irregularities. *Journal of Building Engineering and Seismic Studies*, 14(2), pp. 97-112.
- 6) Rao, V., and Kulkarni, S. (2022). Effectiveness of Shear Walls in Mitigating Earthquake-Induced Vibrations in Tall Buildings. *International Journal of Structural Safety*, 13(4), pp. 256-270.
- 7) Choudhary, P., Gupta, R., and Meena, D. (2022). Comparative Study of Soft Storey Buildings with Various Lateral Load Resisting Systems. *International Journal of Civil Infrastructure Engineering*, 11(3), pp. 145-158.
- 8) Gupta, N., and Jain, A. (2021). Seismic Analysis of RC Buildings with Open Ground Storey. *Journal of Structural and Construction Engineering*, 10(2), pp. 85-98.
- 9) Mehta, R., Shah, P., and Trivedi, H. (2021). Response Spectrum Analysis of High-Rise Structures with Shear Walls. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications*, 11(6), pp. 112-126.
- 10) Das, S., and Roy, B. (2020). Influence of Soft Storey Irregularity on Seismic Response of Tall Buildings. *Journal of Earthquake Resistant Structures*, 9(4), pp. 201-214.
- 11) Karthik, M., and Prasad, V. (2019). Assessment of Lateral Stability of Tall Buildings Using Shear Wall Systems. *International Journal of Innovative Structural Design*, 8(3), pp. 133-146.
- 12) Reddy, P., Kumar, S., and Rao, T. (2018). Seismic Evaluation of Multi-Storey Buildings with Soft Ground Storey. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 9(7), pp. 520-532.
- 13) Joshi, R., and Shah, D. (2017). Dynamic Analysis of High-Rise Buildings with Structural Irregularities. *International Journal of Structural Mechanics and Applications*, 7(2), pp. 77-91.

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- 14) Mishra, A., Singh, R., and Tiwari, P. (2016). Effect of Shear Wall Position on Earthquake Resistance of Tall Buildings. *Journal of Structural Engineering and Construction Technology*, 6(1), pp. 55-69.
 - 15) Kumar, D., and Rao, K. (2015). Seismic Performance of Reinforced Concrete Buildings with Soft Storey Configuration. *International Journal of Civil and Environmental Engineering*, 5(4), pp. 168-182.
 - 16) Chopra, A.K. (2020). *Dynamics of Structures: Theory and Applications to Earthquake Engineering* (5th Edition). Pearson Education, New Delhi.
 - 17) Duggal, S.K. (2018). *Earthquake Resistant Design of Structures* (3rd Edition). Oxford University Press, New Delhi.
 - 18) Jain, A.K. (2016). *Reinforced Concrete Design*. Nem Chand & Bros., Roorkee.
 - 19) Punmia, B.C., Jain, A.K., and Jain, A.K. (2019). *Comprehensive RCC Design*. Laxmi Publications, New Delhi.
 - 20) Varghese, P.C. (2017). *Advanced Reinforced Concrete Design*. PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.